

**CRIMINAL LIABILITY FOR STALKING IN SOME IN SOME
EUROPEAN COUNTRIES**

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Annotation: The article discusses the current concept of "stalking" as a form of violent behavior, its types and features. The article examines the legislation of foreign countries, particularly in the England, Germany, Austria, which have legal liability for stalking at the legislative level. Stalking encroaches on a person's physical and mental health, as well as on his life. Taking into account the public danger of this act, the need to criminalize prosecution in the criminal legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan by establishing criminal liability for it is being considered. The specific location of this norm in the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan is proposed, as well as the objects of this crime are listed.

Key words: stalking, stalker, victim, threat, violence, legislation of European countries, consequence, criminal liability.

The world's population still does not perceive stalking seriously, believing that it is, on the contrary, the attention paid by the stalker to the victim. Most people don't understand how terrible the consequences from persecution can be. Victims of stalking have to change their place of residence, place of work or study, which significantly affects their financial situation and social circle. They have to get used to a new place and conditions in a new way. If the location is found by stalker, the victim has to repeat the above scenario. However, these consequences are not sufficiently negative. There are worse outcomes. Victims of persecution often end up committing suicide because it seems to them that this is the only way out of the

situation. Perhaps many scientists of Uzbekistan will consider that this action can be qualified under article 103 of the Criminal Code, but the disposition of this article states that suicide or attempted suicide is committed by threats, ill-treatment or systematic humiliation of the honor and dignity of a person. During the persecution, there is a systematic violation of freedom of movement, which is the constitutional right of every citizen, therefore it is incorrect to qualify stalking under article 103 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The consequences of stalking can also be rape by a stalker of his victim (Article 118 of the Criminal Code); abduction of the victim (137 of the Criminal Code); premeditated murder (Article 97 of the Criminal Code) and many other grave and especially grave crimes. It is important to understand that psychological violence may not develop into physical violence. At the same time, it can reach such a degree of intensity that the victim commits suicide due to systematic psychological trauma, mental suffering and destruction of self-esteem. [1, p. 83]. Consequently, acting Professor of TSUL Abzalova H. M. he also believes that psychological violence can lead a victim to suicide without the use of physical violence.

It follows from this that there is a huge need to criminalize prosecution in the criminal legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Stalking is already a crime in many foreign countries. For example, it has been enshrined as a crime in the legislation of Canada, the United States, the United Kingdom and Wales, Japan, Germany, Australia and many other States.

The first state to recognize stalking as a criminal offense was the United States in 1992. The followers of this example were countries such as Canada and Australia. As for the countries of Europe, the responsibility for stalking was introduced in the UK, Belgium, Ireland, Holland, Austria and Germany.[2]

In England, stalking is considered similar to harassment, but at the same time it is more aggressive. A stalker has an obsession with the person he is stalking. Based on the legislation of England, stalking may include:

- regular stalking;

- repeated entry into someone else's house without an invitation (violation of private property rights);
- checking someone's use of the Internet, e-mail or other electronic tools of communication;
- being in a place where the stalker knows that his victim often visits;
- watch or spy on anyone;
- identity theft (subscribing to services, buying things in someone's name).

Such behavior is considered stalking if it has been committed more than once. The main criteria that persecution should have is its regularity, obsession, undesirability and repetition. [3]

Another State that recognized persecution as a crime is Germany in 2007. Article 238 of the German Criminal Code states:

Persecution – a person who, in a way of significantly worsening the quality of life of another person, unlawfully and systematically persecutes him by the fact that:

1. looking for the spatial proximity of this person;
2. attempts to establish contact with this person using telecommunication means, other means of communication or through third parties;
3. abusing the personal data of this person;
 - a) orders goods or services for him;
 - b) involves third parties to establish contact with him;
4. threatens this person by causing harm to the life, bodily integrity, health or freedom of himself or another person close to him;
5. causes the death of the victim or his relatives. [4, p. 344]

In Austria, there is also criminal liability for stalking. Section 107a of the Austrian Criminal Code stipulates:

- (1) Anyone who unlawfully and persistently stalks a person (as described in paragraph 2) is subject to one year's imprisonment or a fine of up to 720 daily rates.

(2) Persistently persecutes someone in a way that suits him in his lifestyle, namely unreasonable influence, continuing for a long period of time as follows:

1. trying to establish physical intimacy,
2. attempts to communicate via telecommunications or using another means of communication, or through third parties,
3. orders goods or services for a person using their personal data,
4. forces third parties to contact a person using her/his personal data, records, facts,
5. publication of photos from personal life without the permission of this person.

(3) If the period covered by paragraph 1 exceeds one year, or if the crime involves suicide, or if the person prosecuted within the meaning of paragraph 2 attempts to commit suicide, the perpetrator must be sentenced to imprisonment for up to three years. [5, p. 32]

Nowadays, the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan does not provide for liability for prosecution. Persecution encroaches on the constitutional rights of the victim, (for example, freedom of movement), physical and mental integrity, in general, the health of the victim. Due to the lack of norms that could adequately protect the victims of persecution, the persecutor remains unpunished. If the victim reports stalking, which is expressed in the fact that a person seeks physical intimacy, tries to establish contact with this person using telecommunications or other means of communication or through third parties, forces third parties to contact him, threatens this person with harm to life, physical integrity, health or freedom of himself, one of his relatives or another person close to him, etc., this message remains without consideration, because law enforcement agencies do not qualify them as a crime.

Considering the above, it is proposed to introduce criminal liability for stalking in Chapter 7 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Crimes against the constitutional rights and freedoms of citizens), since this act encroaches

on freedom of movement by the fact that the stalker creates an obstacle for the victim to fully enjoy this right by often appearing in places visited by the object of persecution. In addition, the object of this socially dangerous act will be personal inviolability, inviolability of private life, inviolability of the home, personal data. In most cases, the object can also be the physical and mental health of a person, since a stalker can use violence or the threat of violence. Sometimes a stalker encroaches on the sexual freedom of the victim and even her life, however, these objects will rather act as optional.

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